

THE ESSENCE OF THE INTEGRATIVE APPROACH AS A THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF ECONOMISTS

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Abstract. *The article examines the essence of an integrative approach to the preparation of future economists for professional activity. The theoretical foundations of the professional training of future economists are considered, in particular, attention is paid to basic mathematical training. Based on the integrative approach, a structural and substantive model of the formation of professional competence of future economists is presented.*

Keywords: *integration, integrative approach, content of education, professional activity, educational activity, quasi-professional activity, educational and professional activity, competence.*

Raising the process of training future economists to a qualitatively new level, the professional competence of an economist, his competitiveness in the labor market depend on many factors, including the integrated knowledge of a specialist.

Integration processes in knowledge and cognition systems are in great demand today to develop the readiness of specialists to carry out professional activities in any industry.

The general theoretical characteristics of pedagogical integration are revealed in the works of V.S. Bezrukova [1], A.S. Belkin [2], A.Ya. Danilyuk [6], N.K. Chapaev [12]; the foundations of an integrative approach to the construction of the content of vocational education are presented in the studies of M.N. Berulava [3], V.N. Maksimova [10], V.A. Slastenina [11], I.P. Yakovleva [14] etc.

In the interpretation of V.S. Bezrukova, integration is one of the forms of interrelation of the interaction of objects and phenomena in theory and practice, the restoration of their original natural integrity. At the same time, integration simultaneously acts as a principle, process, result of the interconnection of objects, which indicates the polyfunctionality of this concept [1].

M.N. Berulava understands the integration of the content of education as “the process and the result of the interaction of its structural elements, accompanied by an increase in the consistency and density of students' knowledge” [3].

The pedagogical essence of integration is deeply revealed in the works of N.K. Chapaev, who considers it as a process and result of the development, formation and formation of multidimensional human integrity in the conditions of integrative pedagogical activity [12].

A.V. Makovchik shows the modern requirements for the integration of the content of education and defines the organizational and pedagogical conditions of this process [7].

The integration of education, which is the basis of the integrative approach, appears as a process of convergence and unification of various components of the content of education.

In pedagogy, the content of education is considered as a systematized set of knowledge, skills and attitudes, as well as the development of cognitive abilities achieved as a result of educational work and a certain level of practical training.

The structure of the content of education is important for the educational process.

Higher school has its own peculiarities of building the content of education. In particular, it is primarily focused on professional activity. V.S.Lednev [9] distinguishes the factors that determine the structure of the content of education:

1. Formation of personal qualities that do not depend on the specific subject properties of the activity.
- 2.. The structure of the object of study.
3. Movement from theory to practice.
4. The process of personality formation is individual.
5. Age features.

In addition to general pedagogical principles, the works of V.I.Kagan and I.A.Sychenikov [8] describe specific didactic principles of building the content of education:

1. The principle of conformity of the content to the goals of forming a harmoniously developed personality of a specialist.
2. The principle of compliance of the content of education with the requirements for building an organic integral system of training specialists in higher educational institutions.
3. The principle of compliance of the content of education with scientific and pedagogical requirements.

N. A. Chitalin [13] substantiates the fundamental content of vocational education as a new system built "on the integration of fundamental subject (natural science, humanities, technical, special) concepts and supplemented by basic general cultural, general scientific, interdisciplinary concepts"; formulates "principles of fundamentalization and professionalization, integrity and subject differentiation, completeness and continuity"

From the point of view of modern didactics, two sides are clearly manifested in teaching: teaching (teacher activity) and reading (conscious cognitive activity of students).

V.M. Blinov, exploring reading and teaching as a system of activity, argues that education: 1) this is a special socially coordinated activity; 2) such activity is of a systematic regular nature; 3) the unity of teaching and reading activity is its basis [4].

In accordance with the conceptual foundations of the contextual education technology created by A. A. Verbitsky [5], with the help of a system of forms, methods and means in the educational activities of students, the subject and social content of future professional activity is consistently designed. The subject content of the student's activity is designed as a system of educational problem situations and tasks that reflect the professional functions of graduates in accordance with the direction and level of training. At the same time, three basic forms of students' activities are distinguished: academic-type educational activities (lectures, seminars, independent work, etc.), quasi-professional activities (business games, analysis of specific situations, laboratory work, etc.), educational and professional activities (design, industrial practice, preparation of final qualifying works, etc.). It is obvious that such education, due to its focus on the implementation of the competence approach, acquires a context-competence format, the purpose of which is to form students' abilities to competently perform professional functions, successfully solve problems in the field of future professional activity

The activity approach serves as the basis for research and development of a system of tools for training future economists.

The improvement of the preparation of future economists for professional activity is

achieved by considering the construction of the content of education as an integral system characterized by the essence, principles of integrative education, the activity of the teacher in the formation of integrative knowledge among students, as well as the student's activity in the assimilation of the concept, the purpose of education, the content of teaching, forms, methods and means of teaching.

Consequently, the implementation of an integrative approach to preparing future economists for professional activity, in particular for basic mathematical training, requires not only the content of integral knowledge (the content of educational materials: concepts, method, model), but also the development of methods for organizing the activities of teachers and students for the study of this material.

The activity approach in mathematical education provides an important principle of pedagogical science – the unity of theory and practice. Studying the research of A.A.Verbitsky, we define three main types of activity in mathematical education (educational, quasi-professional, educational professional) (table 1).

Table 1

Type of activity	Content of the activity	Form, method, means of carrying out activities
Educational activities	Knowledge of mathematical concepts and methods. The ability to establish links between economic processes and relevant mathematical knowledge. Mastering the methods and techniques of solving practical problems of economic content.	<i>Form: lectures and practical classes, independent work of the student.</i> <i>Method: methods of scientific research: analysis and synthesis, method of heuristic problems, method of mathematical modeling, use of graphic organizers</i> <i>Tools: subject tasks, computer workshop, tables.</i>
Quasiprofessional activity	The ability to synthesize knowledge in the field of economic and mathematical sciences for the creative solution of economic problems as a means of mastering mathematical methods and models. Selection, justification and application of mathematical methods for solving economic problems. The inclusion of students in the activities of economic and mathematical content using active forms and methods of teaching. Realization of the complexity, consistency and consistency of the application of applied problems of economic content on various topics of mathematics. Mathematical modeling of economic processes, construction of multi-stage tasks for planning, optimization and forecasting of economic processes.	<i>Form: integrative lesson; integrative circle, Olympiads, conferences, student's independent work.</i> <i>Method: work in small groups, game technologies, educational discussions. Bloom's taxonomy, project method.</i> <i>Tools: professionally oriented tasks; situational tasks; tables.</i>

Educational - professional activities	<p>The ability to synthesize knowledge as professional skills in modeling economic processes, the willingness to build mathematical models in solving problems related to professional activity, the use of mathematical methods using experience actively accumulated in a new situation of a creative professional nature. The use of mathematical methods and models in the preparation of research papers, term papers and final qualifying papers (analysis of economic processes, banking and financial transactions), evaluation of their actions and results.</p>	<p><i>Form: term papers and final qualification papers, research work.</i></p> <p><i>Method: problem-based learning method, programmed learning method, project method.</i></p> <p><i>Tools: professional tasks; mathematical modeling method</i></p>
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The formation of the integration of mathematical education in accordance with the types of activities (academic, quasi-professional, educational and professional) is characterized by the following three levels: intra-disciplinary integration, interdisciplinary integration, integrity. Integration levels are defined as the internal basis of an integrative approach to preparing students for professional activity.

Intra-disciplinary integration of science is aimed at establishing meaningful, structural and technological links between departments of the same discipline; this makes it possible to identify the links that make up the system, as well as the links between theory and practice.

Interdisciplinary integration – provides an understanding of the holistic consciousness, the essence of creative activity, methodological training and its implementation at the level of fundamental ideas, principles, methods of various disciplines.

The degree of integrity of integration of mathematical education is a high level of integration of mathematical education, professional problem situations are solved using mathematical knowledge.

In accordance with the three levels of the integration process (integration within the framework of science, interdisciplinary integration and integrity), the formation of mathematical competence of an economist as a result of integration is characterized by the following three levels: basic mathematical, basic professional mathematical and professional mathematical.

Based on the above work, we have developed a structural and substantive model for the formation of professional competence of future economists based on an integrative approach (see Figure 1). The model is used to improve the professional and mathematical training of an economist based on an integrative approach.

The professional competence of an economist, developed at the levels of integration, is determined by the following criteria:

The cognitive criterion is based on knowledge and practical - the relevance of knowledge in solving issues of economic content, the application of knowledge in new economic processes, the effective use of knowledge in practice. The real amount of knowledge, the use of knowledge in new situations, the effectiveness of knowledge in practice.

The activity criterion makes it possible to assess the level of formation of cognitive and practical skills (volume; assimilation of the basic theoretical foundations of the skill; completeness of skills; integrativity; flexibility, etc.).

The personal-professional criterion makes it possible to assess the axiological description of the learning process: the motives of learning, the personality-specific, professional significance of acquired knowledge, satisfaction with the educational process, the dynamics of intellectual and physical development, readiness for independent learning.

The integrative approach in the framework of professional training of future economists is a set of forms and methods that characterize the process and result of the formation of professional competence, accompanied by the growth of systematic knowledge, the complexity of the student's skills, expressed in theoretical and practical preparedness and contributing to the comprehensive development of personality.

Figure 1

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